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DEPENDENCE OF STRAIN AMPLITUDE ON LOSS MECHANISMS IN PLATE RESONATORS

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Abstract

Piezoelectric elements are used in a variety of applications such as optical modulators, microactuators, and certain types of transducers and resonant sensors, where it is necessary to know the maximum amplitude obtainable. Conduction, dielectric, and viscous losses all limit the amplitude.

We consider high frequency crystal plates in the one-dimensional approximation. By the use of a complex piezoelectric coupling coefficient incorporating all three loss mechanisms, the limiting amplitude of the fundamental mode is found. Examples are given for AT, BT, and SC quartz cuts, along with lithium niobate and lead titanate ceramic.

The influence of electrode mass loading on amplitude is also determined, along with the magnitude of the interfacial stress. The stress levels can attain significant levels.

Introduction

The maximum amplitude of vibration of plate resonators is limited by loss. We assume that the losses consist of acoustic viscosity, representable by a motional time constant, and a combination of both dielectric and conduction losses which are lumped into a static time constant. A single fundamental mode is treated for simplicity of illustration.

The presence of the three loss mechanisms is accounted for by making the piezoelectric coupling coefficient complex, while however retaining the individual frequency dependence of each type of loss. One then substitutes this complex coupling factor for the lossless one in the expression for surface displacement of a plate. The additional incorporation of electrode mass loading requires only the further replacement of the coupling factor by the term appearing in parentheses in Eq. 55, p. 126, of [1]. The calculational procedure is sketched below.

In the lossless case, the effect on frequency of mass loading is seen in Fig. 1. Here, resonance frequency displacement, δ_R , defined in [2,3], is plotted against mass loading, μ .

Givens

The following quantities are regarded as specified input values:

Stiffened acoustic velocity, $vbar$
Mass density, ρ
Piezoelectric coupling factor, k (lossless)
Motional time constant, τ_1
Total conductivity, σ_{tot}
Normalized electrode mass loading, μ
Nominal fundamental plate frequency, f_0
Vacuum permittivity, ϵ_0
Permittivity at constant stress, ϵ_{ST}

Derived Quantities

From the givens, the following are calculated:

Permittivity at constant strain, $\epsilon_{PS} = (1 - k^2) \cdot \epsilon_{ST}$
Static time constant, $\tau_0 = (\epsilon_{PS}/\sigma_{tot})$
Stiffened elastic stiffness, $cbar = \rho \cdot (vbar)^2$
Plate half-thickness, $h = vbar/(4 \cdot f_0)$

Variables

Radian frequency, ω
Frequency variable, $f = \omega/2\pi$

Additional Derived Quantities

$L(\omega) = (1 + [1/(j\omega \cdot \tau_0)])$
 $F(\omega) = [(1 - k^2) + (j\omega \cdot \tau_1) + (k^2/L(\omega))]$
Lossy $vbar$, $vbar_l(\omega) = vbar \cdot \sqrt{F(\omega)}$

Lossy normalized frequency variable,

$$Xl(\omega) = (h \bullet \omega) / (vbarl(\omega))$$

Lossy tangent, $Tl(\omega) = \tan(Xl(\omega))$

Lossy tangent X over X, $T(\omega) = Tl(\omega) / Xl(\omega)$

$$G(\omega) = [1 + (\tau_{01} / \tau_{00}) + j\omega \bullet \tau_{01} + (1 - k^2) / (j\omega \bullet \tau_{00})]$$

Lossy coupling squared, $k^2l(\omega) = k^2 / G(\omega)$

$$H(\omega) = k^2l(\omega) / [1 - \mu \bullet Xl(\omega) \bullet Tl(\omega)]$$

$$Go(\omega) = T(\omega) / [1 - H(\omega) \bullet T(\omega)]$$

$$\text{Alpha}(\omega) = \sqrt{\{k^2l(\omega) \bullet \text{epsS} \bullet [\rho \bullet (vbarl(\omega))^2]^{-1}\}}$$

Amplitude and Stress

With the definition:

Gomax = The maximum of $|Go(\omega)|$,
the maximum amplitude per volt applied is

$$U = \text{Alpha} \bullet \text{Gomax},$$

where Alpha is Alpha(ω) evaluated at the value of ω that makes $|Go(\omega)| = \text{Gomax}$.

The acceleration (in earth-gravity units) at the interface between the piezoelectric plate and the electrode is equal to $\omega^2 \bullet U / g$, where $g = 9.81 \text{ m/sec}^2$. The stress at this interface is $\omega^2 \bullet U \bullet \mu$ (pascal).

When the above relations are applied to the numerical values given in Table 1, and computations carried out at $f_0 = 10, 100, \text{ and } 1000 \text{ MHz}$, and for $\mu = 1\% \text{ and } 10\%$, one arrives at the results given in Tables 2, 3, and 4. These tables provide the surface amplitude per volt applied, the surface acceleration, the electrode-resonator interfacial stress, and the stress normalized to the appropriate elastic constant.

The calculations indicate that the electrode thickness can have a significant effect on the interfacial stress. The stress levels are large enough in some cases to approach the point at which electrode detachment can occur. Even if this occurs in a very local and microscopic way, it could be a mechanism producing activity dips [4] and aging.

Breaking Strength of Quartz

It is instructive to compare the tabular values of electrode-resonator interfacial stress to the reported experimental breaking stress of quartz [5,6]. The average tensile breaking strength of quartz is about 0.1 GPa; coincidentally, this is also about the standard pressure at which quartz is grown. The theoretical value is larger. One can estimate it in the following

way: There are about 43.7×10^{23} moles of quartz/ m^3 , so the average "length" associated with a molecule is roughly 3.4 Å. This gives about 8.9×10^{18} molecules/ m^2 on a surface of separation. It requires 4 or 5 eV to break each bond; the maximum Si-O distance (at breakage) is 1.6 Å [7]. Therefore the breaking stress is about 35-45 GPa. Numerical simulations [8] of glass-metal bond separations give about 10-20 GPa.

Conclusions

For quartz, resonant amplitudes are in the Å per volt range; ceramics can have one hundred times greater values. These values are relatively insensitive functions of frequency in the range 10 MHz to 1 GHz.

Electrode mass loadings of 1 % and 10 % deposited on the resonator surface produce large interfacial stresses at resonance. In some cases these stresses approach in value the breaking strength.

References

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Figure 1 Resonance frequency displacement versus mass loading.

TABLE 1. INPUT MATERIAL CONSTANTS

Material/ Cut	rho	vbar	k	tau1	sigtot	epsT
	kg/m ³	m/s	%	ps	pS	pF/m
AT quartz	2649	3322	8.80	11.8	10	40.0
BT quartz	2649	5072	5.62	4.9	10	40.0
SC quartz	2649	3594	4.99	11.7	10	40.0
Li Nb O ₃ 36° rot y	4646	7400	48.7	3	10	7.40 • ε ₀
Ceramic	7520	4400	51	1000	1e+8	263 • ε ₀

TABLE 2. AMPLITUDE AND STRESS; f_o = 10 MHz

Material/ Cut	Amplitude	Accel. at surface	Stress at interface	Stress/ (ρ • vbar ²)	mu, mass loading
	Å/volt	earth-g's	pascal		
AT quartz	7.55	2.96e5	2.90e4	9.9e-7	1 %
	5.32	2.15e5	2.11e5	7.2e-6	10 %
BT quartz	2.08	8.41e4	8.25e3	1.2e-7	1 %
	2.27	9.18e4	9.01e4	1.3e-6	10 %
SC quartz	2.66	1.08e5	1.06e4	3.1e-7	1 %
	2.85	1.15e5	1.13e5	3.3e-6	10 %
Li Nb O ₃	4.37	1.40e5	1.37e4	5.4e-8	1 %
	5.94	2.40e5	2.36e5	9.2e-7	10 %
Ceramic	89.9	2.77e4	2.72e7	1.9e-4	1 %
	798.	2.03e7	1.99e7	1.4e-4	10 %

TABLE 3. AMPLITUDE AND STRESS; $f_0 = 100$ MHz

Material/ Cut	Amplitude	Accel. at surface	Stress at interface	Stress/ ($\rho \cdot vbar^2$)	mu, mass loading
	Å/volt	earth-g's	pascal		
AT quartz	7.55	2.96e7	2.90e6	9.9e-5	1 %
	5.32	2.15e7	2.11e7	7.2e-4	10 %
BT quartz	2.08	8.41e6	8.25e5	1.2e-5	1 %
	2.27	9.18e6	9.01e6	1.3e-4	10 %
SC quartz	2.66	1.06e7	1.05e6	3.1e-5	1 %
	2.85	1.15e7	1.13e7	3.3e-4	10 %
Li Nb O ₃	4.37	1.40e7	1.37e6	5.4e-6	1 %
	5.96	2.41e7	2.36e7	9.3e-5	10 %
Ceramic	89.3	2.75e8	2.70e7	1.9e-4	1 %
	503.	1.29e9	1.26e9	8.7e-3	10 %

TABLE 4. AMPLITUDE AND STRESS; $f_0 = 1000$ MHz

Material/ Cut	Amplitude	Accel. at surface	Stress at interface	Stress/ ($\rho \cdot vbar^2$)	mu, mass loading
	Å/volt	earth-g's	pascal		
AT quartz	7.55	2.95e9	2.89e8	9.9e-3	1 %
	5.32	2.15e9	2.11e9	7.2e-2	10 %
BT quartz	2.08	8.41e8	8.25e7	1.2e-3	1 %
	2.27	9.18e8	9.01e8	1.3e-2	10 %
SC quartz	2.66	1.08e9	1.06e8	3.1e-3	1 %
	2.85	1.15e9	1.13e9	3.3e-2	10 %
Li Nb O ₃	4.23	1.35e9	1.33e8	5.2e-4	1 %
	5.66	2.29e9	2.25e9	8.8e-3	10 %
Ceramic	61.6	1.90e10	1.86e9	1.3e-2	1 %
	64.4	1.64e10	1.61e10	1.1e-1	10 %